

PERCEPTION AND KNOWLEDGE ABOUT APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN IMPLANT DENTISTRY AMONG IMPLANTOLOGISTS OF CENTRAL INDIA - A QUESTIONNAIRE-BASED STUDY

Dr. Ravina A. Khairkar¹, Dr. Krishankumar S. Lahoti², Dr. B.S. Shylesh Kumar³, Dr. Sayali P. Nikode⁴,
Dr.Zehra rana⁵, Dr. Sharwari P. Bhatkar⁶

Department of Prosthodontics,

Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital,Nagpur.

Abstract

Background – The use of Artificial Intelligence has been explicitly trending amongst dentists in every aspect of dentistry, likewise it has many applications in implantology. **Aim** – this cross-sectional study aims to assess knowledge, Perspective, and Implementation of about application of artificial intelligence in implant dentistry among implantologists in central India. **Methodology** - The study was conducted amongst implantologists of central India who have performed more than 20 implants with a sample size of 97. The questionnaire from the study of Tim Eschert et al was modified and used with due permission of the author in Google Forms, was circulated among Implantologists of central India and the responses were recorded. **Results** – It was seen that 26.80%, 48.45%, 21.65% of respondents considered their knowledge concerning applications of artificial intelligence as above average, average, and excellent respectively. Maximum participants used AI for recognizing implant type by using radiographic images (77.32%) and predicting implant success (11.34%) younger practitioners perceived the applications and knowledge better as compared to older practitioners. Participants had a conviction that AI in implantology would reduce iatrogenic errors but also impact the workforce needed. **conclusion** - Discernments into the acceptance and use of AI in implantology have been divulged lately within the limitations of the study.

Key words – Implantologists, Artificial Intelligence, Knowledge, Perception.

I.INTRODUCTION

Due to its many uses, Artificial Intelligence (AI) in dentistry and medicine has caught the interest of researchers recently.^{[1][2]} It can serve as a potent diagnostic tool to help and optimize dental implant designs, identify dental implants using radiographic imaging, and forecast implant survival.^[3] The introduction of AI in clinical settings is important in harmonizing a panoramic educational program and successful implant treatment,^[4] hence, the study aims to scrutinize the knowledge and perceptions regarding the application of AI in implant dentistry of dental implantologists in central India.

II.METHODOLOGY –

A. Study design - This is a cross-sectional questionnaire study.

B. Study setting - The study was conducted amongst implantologists of central India who have performed more than 20 implants.

C. Sample size – sample size was calculated considering the proportion of study subjects knowing Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Implant Dentistry as the main outcome measure. A pilot study was conducted on 12 subjects where 58.3% had above-average knowledge. For a 95% confidence interval with 10% absolute precision a sample size of 97 is considered sufficient to estimate true parameter value in the target population.

D. Sampling method - A random sample of 97 subjects who fulfilled eligibility criteria and consented to participate in this survey were selected from a sampling frame available with the local dentist association.

E. Study method - A specially prepared web-designed survey in Google Forms was circulated among Implantologists of central India and the responses were recorded. The questionnaire from the study of Tim Eschert et al was modified and used with due permission of the author. The questionnaire included 1 open open-ended question and 20 close-ended questions related to, perspective and knowledge about artificial intelligence in implant dentistry among implantologists of central India. The Inclusion and Exclusion criteria are described in Table 1.

Table 1 – Inclusion and Exclusion criteria.
Inclusion criteria
Implantologists practicing in central India
Implantologists who have performed more than 20 implants
Exclusion criteria –
Dental practioners, practicing conventional Dentistry.
Implantologists practicing other than in central India
Implantologists who have performed less than 20 implants

F. Data analysis – Data was analysed and loaded in a statistical software STATA Version 10.1 2011 by Stata Corp, Texas USA. This is a descriptive study where % of subjects having knowledge, awareness, about Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Implant Dentistry was estimated along with 95% confidence interval.

Test of significance like pearsons chi square test were applied to assess difference in perception and knowledge in respective fields of dentistry. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

III.RESULTS

The Google form was distributed to a total of 97 subjects among which two were endodontists, 15 were general dentists, 17 were oral and maxillofacial surgeons, 17 were periodontists, 35 were prosthodontists, and the remaining 11 were from other branches of dentistry. Maximum participants 57.73% were from the age group of 25-30 years and 35 (36.08%) practicing for five to ten years. 39 participants (40.21) were from urban and 27 (27.84%) were from somewhat urban work environments.

Maximum respondents used AI sometimes (43.30%) and occasionally (38.14%) in their work and 90.72% of respondents used artificial intelligence in implantology practice. 26.80%, 48.45%, and 21.65% of respondents considered their knowledge concerning applications of artificial intelligence as above average, average, and excellent respectively, only 2.06 % and 1.03% of participants rated their knowledge as very poor and bad (fig. 1) Maximum participants used AI for recognizing implant type by using radiographic image (77.32%) and predict implants success (11.34%) (Table 2) whereas, 82.47% participants believed that the most important. Maximum respondents strongly agreed to the fact that AI will lead to a reduction of iatrogenic error in their profession (fig. 5). 26 participants answered the open-ended questions suggesting improvements and steps to be taken to prepare implantology for AI, as 66% of participants believed that their profession is well equipped for application of AI and 16% being unsure and 15% being reluctant about it (Table 5). The correlation of age and profession and their area of application of AI are given in Table 3,4 and Fig. 6,7.

Table 2. Distribution of subjects according to aspect for use of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Response	No.	%
To predict risk Factors and ontology criteria	1	1.03
Optimize implant designs	3	3.09
Predict implant success by using patient risk factors	11	11.34
To recognize implant type by using radiographical image.	75	77.32
Total	90	92.78

Table 3. Distribution of subjects according to their age and by their profession

Age (years)	2. What is your profession?											
	Endodontics		General dentistry		Oral and Maxillofacial surgery		Periodontology		Prosthodontics		Other	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
25 - 35	1	50	11	73.33	6	35.29	11	100	7	41.18	20	57.14
36 - 55	1	50	1	6.67	5	29.41	0	0	8	47.06	12	34.29
≥ 55	0	0.00	3	20.00	6	35.29	0	0	2	11.76	3	8.57
Total	2	100	15	100	17	100	11	100	17	100	35	100
P value	0.003 (Significant)											

Table 4. Distribution of subjects according to their Age (years) by area of application of AI include Implantology				
Age group (years)	Q8. Does your area of application of AI include Implantology?			
	Yes		No	
	No.	%	No.	%
25 - 35	47	53.41	9	100.00
36 - 55	27	30.68	0	0.00
≥ 55	14	15.91	0	0.00
Total	88	100	9	100
P value	0.026 (Significant)			
Perception of respondents regarding whether their area of application of AI include implantology was significantly different in younger versus older practitioner ($P < 0.05$).				

Table 5. Distribution of subjects according to measures should be taken to Prepare implantology for the application of AI		
Response	No.	%
Awareness and knowledge about Digital Dentistry should be increased	13	13.40
Cost effectiveness	5	5.15
Design	1	1.03
Training	5	5.15
Practice	1	1.03
No	1	1.03
Total	26	26.80

IV.DISCUSSION

McCarthy first used the term artificial intelligence (AI) to describe automated machines that replicate human intellect through reasoning.^{[1][2]} Applications of AI have been documented for creating prediction models based on patient risk factors and ontology criteria to assess osteointegration success or implant prognosis, as well as for optimising dental implant designs through the integration of AI models with finite element analysis (FEA) calculations.

Nevertheless, there is a dearth of research on the development performance of AI approach and its possible impact on implant dentistry.

^[4] The AI models used in the research to forecast osteointegration or implant success ranged from 62.4% to 80.5%. ^[4] While AI models are still in their infancy, Revilla-León et al. claim that they can already recognise the kind of implant, forecast implant success based on patient risk factors and ontology criteria, and improve implant designs.^[2] The more advanced use of AI in implant dentistry was demonstrated by the models created to identify the kind of implant using radiographic pictures, which had an overall accuracy range from 93.8% to 98%, according to the evaluated research.^[5]

This study states that implantologists from Central India have sufficiently good knowledge about application of AI in Implant Dentistry. As maximum participants were from the age group of 25-35 and belonged from all the branches of dentistry, it can be stated that the younger practitioners have greater knowledge and perceive the application of AI better as compared to older practitioners. Not only this, but 100% of the younger practitioners are also seen practicing implantology and majority uses AI. Hence, the generational gap and knowledge gap can be correlated. The objective of the study cannot be determined based on the speciality of dentists as the sampling was randomized. However, nevertheless the fact that not only periodontists, prosthodontists, oral and maxillofacial surgeons but rest specialities of dentistry are also practicing implantology with the application of AI is suggestive of its influence. Most of the participants are using AI for recognizing implant type as well for surgical guidance in implantology and think that the greatest advantage of using AI in implantology is better access to disease screening and better surgical guidance and hence it reduces iatrogenic errors in clinical practice. Most participants think that the main concerning fact about AI with respect to data and technology as well as clinical aspect is regarding outsourcing step rather than challenging the patient doctor relationship, also, that AI will decrease the workforce needed. It can be stated from the results that, as majority of participants strongly agreed, AI has greatly impacted the workforce needed in this decade and in the coming decade. As maximum participants were from urban and somewhat urban areas the practitioners from rural areas are lagging in terms of usage and the beneficence of AI can be ruled out hence, according to responses obtained in the study, training programs, modules, about digital dentistry and broadcast of recently developed technologies and machineries should be conducted periodically, so that all the implantologists population could get aware and benefited as 16% participants still are unsure whether their profession is well equipped for application of AI and 15% participants have no faith into it. The fact that recently developing machinery are expensive, cost-effectiveness should also be a factor to be considered. It can be clearly said that a large population of implantologists are not only making use but are being dependent on AI. One must make note of advancement should be used for progression and not for reliance.

The study has given professionals from central India the opportunity to indicate the necessary steps for introducing AI in clinical, as it is important regarding harmonizing a panoramic educational program and successful implant treatment.

V.LIMITATIONS

The sample size of 97 is not fully representative of population of implantologists in central India. Due to voluntary participation response bias cannot be eliminated.

VI.CONCLUSION

Within the limitations of this study, discernment of embracing and use of AI in implantology are divulged for the newly.

QUESTIONNAIRE

1.How old are you?

-25 – 35

-36 - 55

-56 and above

2. What is your profession?

- General dentistry
- Oral and maxillofacial surgery
- Endodontics
- Periodontology
- Prosthodontics
- Pedodontics
- Other

3. Since when do you work in your profession?

In training

- <5 years
- 5–10 years
- 20–30 years
- More than 30 years

4. Work environment

- Rural
- Somewhat rural
- Somewhat urban
- Urban

5. Do you practice Implantology?

- Yes
- No

6. Number of implants placed till now

- <20
- 20
- >20

7. How often do you use artificial intelligence in your daily work?

- Never
- Occasionally
- Sometimes
- Often
- Always

8. Does your area of application of AI include Implantology?

-Yes - No

9. If yes, in comparison to your colleagues in your profession how would you rate your knowledge in the topic of AI and its application possibilities in Implantology?

-Excellent

-Above average

-Average

-Below average

-Very poor

10. In which aspect do you use AI in Implantology?

-To recognize implant type by using radiographical Image

Predict implant success by using patient risk

--Factors and ontology criteria

-Optimize implant designs

11. What extent do you expect AI to impact the workforce needed in Implantology in this decade?

-To a great extent

-Somewhat

-Very little

12. To what extent do you expect AI to impact the workforce needed in Implantology in the next decade?

-To a great extent

-Somewhat

-Very little

13. How will AI impact the workforce needed?

-Increase

-Decrease

-None

14. Is your profession adequately equipped for the application of AI?

-Yes

-No

-Unsure

15. What measures should be taken to Prepare implantology for the application of AI?

16. Can you imagine implementing the following workflow in your clinical life: Radiographs of a patient are diagnosed by an AI. A specialist evaluates the radiographs and the AI's findings.

-Yes

-No

-Unsure

17. Which of the following advantages regarding the application of AI in Implantology are most important?

-Better access to disease-screening

-More targeted referrals

-More cost-efficient healthcare

-Better diagnostics

-Less time-consuming monotonous tasks

-Better surgical guidance

18. Which of the following aspect are the most concerning regarding the data and technology companies' application of AI in Implantology?

-Concerns regarding the out sourcing of the steps of procedure to large data and technology companies

-Concerns over accountability and responsibility in case of machine Privacy and data security concerns

19. Which of the following aspect are the most concerning regarding the application of AI in Clinical life?

-Concerns regarding the outsourcing steps of procedure to large data and technology companies

-Concerns over accountability and responsibility in case of machine errors

-Privacy and data security concerns

-Lack of trust in diagnostic capability of the AI

-Reduced demand for specialist groups

-Concerns regarding the benchmarking between clinicians and AI

-Challenge for the patient–doctor relationship

-Consequences for the workforce

20. To what extent do you agree with the following statement: "The introduction of AI will lead to improvement in my profession."

-Strongly agree

-Agree

-Neither agree or disagree

-Disagree

-Strongly disagree

21. To what extent do you agree the following statement: "The introduction of AI will reduce iatrogenic errors in my profession."

-Strongly agree

-Agree

-Neither agree or disagree

-Disagree

-Strongly disagree

REFERENCES

1. Agrawal P, Nikhade P. Artificial Intelligence in Dentistry: Past, Present, and Future. *Cureus*. 2022 Jul 28;14(7):e27405.
2. Revilla-León M, Gómez-Polo M, Vyas S, Barmak BA, Galluci GO, Att W, Krishnamurthy VR. Artificial intelligence applications in implant dentistry: A systematic review. *J Prosthet Dent*. 2023 Feb;129(2):293-300.
3. Eschert T, Schwendicke F, Krois J, Bohner L, Vinayahalingam S, Hanisch M. A Survey on the Use of Artificial Intelligence by Clinicians in Dentistry and Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery. *Medicina (Kaunas)*. 2022 Aug 5;58(8):1059.
4. Ahmed N, Abbasi MS, Zuberi F, Qamar W, Halim MSB, Maqsood A, Alam MK. Artificial Intelligence Techniques: Analysis, Application, and Outcome in Dentistry-A Systematic Review. *Biomed Res Int*. 2021 Jun 22;2021:9751564.
5. Pareek, Mitali, and Brahmansh Kaushik. "Artificial intelligence in prosthodontics: a scoping review on current applications and future possibilities." *Int J Adv Med* 9 (2022): 367.
6. Reissmann D, Schierz O, Szentpétery A, John MT. Improved perceived general health is observed with prosthodontic treatment. *J Dentist*. 2011;39(2):326- 31.
7. Lee J, Jeong S. Efficacy of deep convolutional neural network algorithm for the identification and classification of dental implant systems, using panoramic and periapical radiographs: a pilot study. *Medicine*. 2020;99(6):20787.
8. Revilla-León M, Gómez-Polo M, Vyas S, Barmak BA, Gal-lucci GO, MutluÖzcan WA, et al. Artificial intelligence models for tooth-supported fixed and removable prosthodontics: a systematic review. *J Prosthet Dentist*. 2021.
9. Al-Johany SS, Andres C. ICK classification system for partially edentulous arches. *J Prosthodont*. 2008;17:502-7.
10. Takahashi T, Nozaki K, Gonda T, Ikebe K. A system for designing removable partial dentures using artificial intelligence. Part 1. Classification of partially edentulous arches using a convolutional neural network. *J Prosthodont Res*. 2021;65(1):115- 8.
11. Saghiri, M.A.; Garcia-Godoy, F.; Gutmann, J.L.; Lotfi, M.; Asgar, K. The Reliability of Artificial Neural Network in Locating Minor Apical Foramen: A Cadaver Study. *J. Endod*. 2012, 38, 1130–1134.